

INDUSTRIAL ROTARY FREQUENCY CONVERTER MACHINE TO GENERATE HIGHER FREQUENCY TO DRIVE SQUIRREL CAGE MACHINES FROM 120Hz POWER SOURCE

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Abstract: *Industrial rotary frequency converter machine to generate higher frequency to drive squirrel cage machines from 120Hz power source is presented. Rotary frequency converters are machines that convert power from one frequency to another. They were commonly used to provide DC power for commercial, industrial and railway electrification from an AC power source. And It works by converting the input AC into rotary mechanical power. Meaning, the input power spins a motor. This motor transmits its power to the generator, which converts the mechanical power into the required AC output power. Squirrel cage induction machines are widely used in industrial and domestic. The rotor is cylindrical mounted on the shaft that contains copper or aluminum bars. Due to its ruggedness in construction and low maintenance found applications in industrial drives, mills, turning machines, pump, fan and blowers. Synchronous machines may be used along with squirrel cage induction machine may be used as a frequency converter to generate a frequency different from that of the utility company. The squirrel cage machine revolves faster, because the squirrel cage machine speed is slightly less than twice the 60Hz synchronous speed of 1800r/min it received from 120Hz power from the rotor of the frequency converter. As the speed was vary, the rotor was turning at 900r/min in the same direction as the rotating stator magnetic field, only 30Hz frequency was generated by the machine and frequency of 90Hz was generated it revolved at 900r/min in the opposite direction of the rotating field. When a six-pole industrial rotary frequency converter machine was connected with a nominal speed of 1200r/min and driven by a 3600r/min squirrel cage induction machine, the highest frequency that was obtained in the combination was a 60Hz input to the stator of the wound rotor machine creates a magnetic field rotating at 1200r/min, and the squirrel cage machine turns the rotor at 3600r/min in the opposite direction to the rotating stator magnetic field thus, generate a frequency of 240Hz as highest. While the lowest when the squirrel cage machine turns the rotor at 3600r/min in the same direction as the rotating stator magnetic field, the field cut the rotor winding at 2400r/min and generated frequency was 120Hz. (There was some slip due to the machines that makes both frequencies became slightly lower. Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter machine speed was increased to drive the industrial machine faster. This was achieved by connecting the stator of the industrial rotary frequency converter machine to 60Hz power supply and the rotor been driven at 1800r/min by the synchronous machine. The direction of rotation was opposite to that of the resolving magnetic field*

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created by the stator windings and turning the frequency of the rotor output voltage to 120Hz. Because; the electrical power delivered by a rotary frequency converter comes from two sources: The electrical power supply to which the stator windings are connected and the mechanical power delivered to rotating rotor shaft. The machine revolves faster in speed and this method can be used to drives an industrial machine where faster and higher speed is requires. This is recommended for machine designers, Engineers and industries when the industrial machines require faster and higher speed.

Keywords: *Frequency, Converter, Rotary, Squirrel cage, Synchronous, Magnetics field, Rotor, Stator and Industry.*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Industrial rotary frequency converter machine to generate higher frequency to drive squirrel cage machines from 120Hz power source is presented. Rotary frequency converters are machines that convert power from one frequency to another. They were commonly used to provide DC power for commercial, industrial and railway electrification from an AC power source. And it works by converting the input AC into rotary mechanical power. Meaning, the input power spins a motor. This motor transmits its power to the generator, which converts the mechanical power into the required AC output power. [1, 8] Synchronous machines may be used along with squirrel cage induction machine may be used as a frequency converter to generate a frequency different from that of the utility company. Squirrel cage induction machines are widely used in industrial and domestic. The rotor is cylindrical mounted on the shaft that contains copper or aluminum bars. Due to its ruggedness in construction and low maintenance found applications in industrial drives, mills, turning machines, pump, fan and blowers. The stator of the wound rotor induction motor connected to the 60Hz power supply and the rotor been driven at 1800r/min by the synchronous motor. [1, 6] The direction of rotation will be opposite to that of the resolving magnetic field created by the stator windings and as a result of this, the frequency of the rotor output voltage is 120Hz. This is because; the electrical power delivered by a rotary frequency converter comes from two sources: The electrical power supply to which the stator windings are connected and the mechanical power delivered to rotating rotor shaft. [3, 5]. When the output frequency is doubled, the mechanical power and the electrical power to the stator are equal. Thus, the rotary frequency converter delivers twice as much electric power to its load as its stator receives. The difference comes from the source of mechanical power driving factor. Rotary frequency converters of this type are employed in industry to generate the higher frequencies necessary to drive small, high-speed induction machines. [1, 9]

2.0 Mathematical Modeling of Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter Machine

For a balanced pure sinusoidal three phase supply, the sum of the three phases, Voltages are zero; as a result, the zero-sequence voltage will be zero. The voltage Transformation in the stator reference frame for this type of source

can be written as [2, 7]. The dynamic performance of Industrial rotary frequency converter machine has received less attention from the researchers; this is mainly because of the non-linearity involved in the Industrial rotary frequency converter machine dynamic equation. The fourth-order ordinary

differential equation which describe the electrical model and the second order ordinary differential equation which describe the mechanical model of the Industrial rotary frequency converter machine are generally non-linear. Analytical solution is usually very difficult consequently, numerical method of analysis using Runge-Kutta fourth order is conveniently applied [7, 8]. Accurate knowledge of run-up synchronization and response to sudden load variations of the Industrial rotary frequency converter machine during dynamic operation is very important especially when designing the Industrial rotary frequency converter machine and can be classified into electrical and mechanical model. [2, 4]

3.0 Electrical Modeling of Industrial rotary frequency converter machine

The d-q axis representation of a Industrial rotary frequency converter machine when the reference frame in the rotor is given by [2, 7],

$$v_q = r_s i_q + \frac{d\lambda_q}{dt} + \lambda_d \omega_r \quad (1)$$

$$v_d = r_s i_d + \frac{d\lambda_d}{dt} - \lambda_q \omega_r \quad (2)$$

$$0 = r_{kq} i_{kq} + \frac{d\lambda_{kq}}{dt} \quad (3)$$

$$0 = r_{kd} i_{kd} + \frac{d\lambda_{kd}}{dt} \quad (4)$$

Expressing equations (1-4) in state variable form with flux linkages as state vectors [2, 10]

$$\dot{\lambda}_q = v_q - \omega_r \lambda_d + \frac{r_s}{L_{ls}}(\lambda_{mq} - \lambda_q) \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{\lambda}_d = v_d + \omega_r \lambda_q + \frac{r_s}{L_{lx}}(\lambda_{md} - \lambda_d) \quad (6)$$

$$\dot{\lambda}_{kq} = \frac{r_{kq}}{L_{lkq}}(\lambda_{mq} - \lambda_{kq}) \quad (7)$$

$$\dot{\lambda}_{kd} = \frac{r_{kd}}{L_{lkd}}(\lambda_{md} - \lambda_{kd}) \quad (8)$$

Where

$$\lambda_{mq} = L_{MQ} \left(\frac{\lambda_q}{L_{ls}} + \frac{\lambda_{kq}}{L_{lkq}} \right) \square \quad (9)$$

$$\lambda_{md} = L_{MD} \left(\frac{\lambda_d}{L_{ls}} + \frac{\lambda_{kd}}{L_{lkq}} + i_{fm} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$L_{MQ} = \frac{(L_{mq}L_{lkq}L_{ls})}{(L_{lkq}L_{ls} + L_{mq}L_{ls} + L_{mq}L_{lkq})} \quad (11)$$

$$L_{MD} = \frac{(L_{md}L_{lkq}L_{ls})}{(L_{lkq}L_{ls} + L_{md}L_{ls} + L_{md}L_{lkq})} \quad (12)$$

$$L_d = L_{ls} + L_{md} \quad (13)$$

$$L_q = L_{ls} + L_{mq} \quad (14)$$

$$i_q = \frac{\lambda_q - \lambda_{mq}}{L_{ls}} \quad (15)$$

$$i_d = \frac{\lambda_d - \lambda_{md}}{L_{ls}} \quad (16)$$

$$i_{kq} = \frac{\lambda_{kq} - \lambda_{mq}}{L_{lkq}} \quad (17)$$

$$i_{kd} = \frac{\lambda_{kd} - \lambda_{md}}{L_{lkq}} \quad (18)$$

Figure 1b: Equivalent circuit of (a) Direct Axis (b) Quadrature Axis of Industrial rotary frequency converter machine form using the derived equations

Industrial rotary frequency converter machine torque has three main components, these three components are: reluctance torque, Synchronous torque, Excitation torque. [2, 7, 11]

Motor torque

$$T_{em} = 1.5 p (\lambda_d i_q - \lambda_q i_d) \quad (19)$$

Reluctance Torque

$$T_r = 1.5 P (L_d - L_q) i_d i_q \quad (20)$$

Synchronous Torque

$$T_{syn} = 1.5 P (L_{md} i_{kd} i_q - L_{mq} i_{kq} i_q) \quad (21)$$

Excitation Torque

$$T_{ex} = 1.5 P L_{md} i_{fm} i_q \quad (22)$$

Where P is the number of pole pairs and assume the line voltage are balanced, Thus, the d-q voltages in terms of the load angle become,

$$V_d = -V \sin \delta \quad (23)$$

$$V_q = V \cos \delta \quad (24)$$

The stator current phase is related to the d-q currents [2, 7]

$$i_{ax} = i_q \quad (25)$$

$$i_{bx} = -\frac{1}{2} i_q - \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} i_d \quad (26)$$

$$i_{cx} = -\frac{1}{2} i_q + \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} i_d \quad (27)$$

4.0 Mechanical Model of Industrial rotary frequency converter machine

Swing equation equations (3.41-3.42), the mechanical model of the Industrial rotary frequency converter machine which allows the inertia and mechanical load torque to be incorporated. [5, 8, 12]

$$\dot{\delta} = \omega_b - \omega_r \tag{28}$$

$$\dot{\omega}_r = \frac{p}{j_m} (T_{em} - T_L) \tag{29}$$

The mechanical model of Industrial rotary frequency converter machine comprises the equations of motion for the industrial rotary frequency converter machine driven load in second order differential equation [2, 7, 12] The mechanical model for Industrial rotary frequency converter machine diagram is shown in figure 2.

$$J_m \frac{d^2\theta_m}{dt^2} = T_c - T_L \tag{30}$$

Decomposing equation (30) into two first order differential equation gives,

$$P\theta_m = \omega_m \tag{31}$$

$$J_m (P \omega_m) = T_c - T_L \tag{32}$$

Figure 2: Mechanical model of Industrial rotary frequency converter machine.

$$P \omega_m = \frac{1}{J_m} (T_c - T_L) \tag{33}$$

But

$$\omega_r = \omega_m P \tag{34}$$

$$\theta_r = \theta_m P \tag{35}$$

Mechanical model of Industrial rotary frequency converter machine was developed according to the principles of the stator iron and the Frame. [5, 7] The values of the [5, 7] Machine resistances and capacitances were calculated according to the principles reported by [4, 5, 11]. Table 2 shows the computed values. The developed electrical model gives rise to a set of differential equations which describe the electromechanical behaviors of the [5, 7] Industrial rotary frequency converter machine under dynamic conditions. MATLAB m-files were developed in other to determine the average values in the various parts of the Industrial rotary frequency converter machine as well as losses in the machine [3, 9, 12] The MATLAB m-files use the Runge-Kutta numerical method [1, 6, 7] to solve the state variable.

5.0 Laboratory Experiment on Industrial rotary frequency converter machine to generate higher frequency to operate three phase squirrel cage machines from 120Hz power source

A laboratory experiment was carried out in the standard research UNIPOINT laboratory to investigate Industrial rotary frequency converter machine to generate higher frequency to operate three phase squirrel cage machines from 120Hz power source.

Materials, Instruments and Components: The materials, instruments and components used are as follows: Wound rotor induction machine, Synchronous machine, three phase Squirrel cage machine, Resistance Module, Three-Phase Wattmeter Module, Power Supply Module (0-220/400V three phase, 220Vdc), AC Metering Module (2.5/2.5/2.5A), AC Metering Module (250/250V), Hand Tachometer, Connection Leads, Timing Belt.

Using the instrument, materials and components, the circuit was as shown in figure 1a. The stator of the synchronous motor was connected to power supply 400V three phase output, terminals 1, 2, and 3. The rotor of the synchronous motor was connected to power supply 220Vdc output, terminals 8 and N. The stator of the three-phase squirrel cage machine was connected through the wattmeter, to the variable power supply 400V three phase output of the, terminals 4, 5, and 6. The rotor windings were terminated at the delta connected resistance load 'R_L'. The synchronous machine was couple to the three-phase squirrel cage machine rotor frequency converter with the timing belt. The load resistance switches were adjusted to their open positions. The field control rheostat of the synchronous machine was set at its full anti clockwise position for maximum resistance. The synchronous machine switch S, was set to the open position. The power supply was turn "ON" and, the machine started running. The synchronous machine switch 'S' was close. The power supply voltage $E_1 = 400\text{Vac}$. was measured and recorded. It was observed that E_2 was zero; it means that the rotor was revolving in the same direction as the magnetic field of the stator. Then, power supply was Turn "OFF" and interchange of the two of the leads to the stator was made. DC excitation of the synchronous machine was adjusted so that current 'I₃' is at its minimum value. The E_2 , I_2 , W_1 , and W_2 was measured and recorded as: $E_2 = 400\text{Vac}$, $I_2 = 0\text{Aac}$, $I_2 = 1.12\text{Aac}$, $W_1 = -20\text{W}$, $W_2 = 92\text{W}$.

Figure3a: Circuit Diagram on Laboratory Investigation on industrial rotary frequency converter machine to generate higher frequency to operate three phase squirrel cage machines from 120Hz power source. (Delta connected resistance load) [UNIPORT LABORATORY]

Three-phase resistance loading was gradually increased by adjusting each resistance section to 240 ohms and E_2 , I_2 , I_1 , W_1 , and W_2 was Measure and record as: $E_2 = 175\text{Vac}$, $I_2 = 1.25\text{Aac}$, $I_1 = 1.0\text{ A ac}$, $W_1 = 63\text{W}$, $W_2 = 198\text{W}$. The load was removed by opening the resistance switches. The voltage was return to zero and the power supply was turn “OFF”. The real power delivered to the stator and the real power delivered to the delta connected load was calculate thus: $\text{power to stator } W_1 + W_2 = 643 + 198 = 261\text{ W}$ and $\text{power to load } E_2 \times I_2 \times 1.73 = 175 \times 1.25 \times 1.73 = 218.75 \times 1.73 = 378\text{ W}$.

Industrial rotary frequency converter machine was replaced with the delta connected resistance load with the delta (wye) connected machine load as shown in Figure 1b. The power supply was turn “ON” and adjust until $E_1 = 400\text{Vac}$.

The squirrel cage machine speed was Measure and record as: I_1 , I_2 , E_2 , W_1 , and W_2 . Thus, $E_2 = 196\text{Vac}$, $I_2 = 0.35\text{ A ac}$, $I_1 = 0.8\text{ Ac}$, $W_1 = -28\text{ W}$, $W_2 = 128\text{ W}$, $r/\text{min} = 3570$. The voltage was returned to zero and the power supply was turned “OFF”. The results of the tests and the parameters of the machine used are shown in Table 1 and 2

Table1: Industrial rotary frequency converter machine parameters in simulation model.

Stator leakage inductance	2.59Mh
q-axis rotor leakage inductance	40.61Mh
d-axis rotor resistance	0.8113Ω
q-axis rotor resistance	1.6226Ω
q-axis magnetizing inductance	40.69Mh
d-axis magnetizing inductance	19.05mH
d-axis rotor leakage inductance	18.97mH
Load torque	7.63Nm
Motor inertial	0.01986Kgm ²
Rated voltage	230V(208V, 255V)

Source: [2,7].

Figure3b: Circuit Diagram of Laboratory Investigation on industrial rotary frequency converter machine to generate higher frequency to operate three phase squirrel cage machines from 120Hz power source. (Replaced with the delta connected resistance load with the delta (wye) connected machine load) [UNIPORT LABORATORY]

Table2: Result Of Experimental on Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter Machine To Generate Higher Frequency To Operate Three Phase Squirrel Cage Machines From 120Hz Power Source.

I₂ (AMPS)	E₁ (VOLTS)	I₁ (Amp)	POWER (VA)	W₁	W₂	POWER (Watts)	PF
0	400	0.79	287	-46	113	66	0.24
0.1	400	0.61	234	-36	92	55	0.24
0.2	400	0.45	165	-16	69	52	0.33
0.3	400	0.23	85.3	10	39	49	0.59
0.4	400	0.13	49.3	24	24	49	0.99
0.5	400	0.19	71.0	39	10	49	0.71
0.6	400	0.34	125	65	-11	53	0.44
0.7	400	0.51	186	79	-23	55	0.31
0.8	400	0.67	244	99	-34	64	0.28

Figure 4: Graph of Stator phase currents versus time function for Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter machine at run-up condition

Figure 5: Graph of axis current I_D and I_Q against time for Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter machine at run up condition

Figure 6: Graph of axes voltages V_D and V_Q against Time for Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter Machine at run up condition

Figure 7: Graph of Torque versus Time function of Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter machine at run up condition

Figure 8: Graph of Copper losses Against Time for Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter machine at run up condition

Figure 9: Graph of Excitation Torque against time for Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter machine at run-up Condition

Figure 10: Graph of Reluctance Torque against time for Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter at run-up Condition

Figure 11: Graph of Rotor Speed against Time for Varying Stator Resistance for Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter machine at run-up Condition.

Figure 12: Graph of Rotor Speed against Time for Varying Stator Resistance for Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter machine at run-up Condition

Figure13: Graph of Electromagnetic Torque against Rotor speed for Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter machine at run-up Condition.

The stator of the Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter machine connected to the 60Hz power supply and the rotor driven at 1800r/min by the synchronous machine. The direction of rotation is opposite to that of the revolving magnetic field created by the stator windings and consequently, the frequency of the rotor output voltage is 120Hz. This is because the electrical power delivered by a rotary frequency converter comes from two sources.

The electrical power supply to which the stator windings are connected, and the mechanical power delivered to rotating rotor shaft.

Where the output frequency is doubled, the mechanical power and the electrical power to the stator are equal, and then the rotary frequency converter delivers twice as much as electric power to its load as its stator receives. The difference comes from the source of mechanical power driving factor. This type of rotary frequency converters is employed in industry to generate the higher frequencies necessary to drive small, high-speed squirrel cage machines.

It was observed that the squirrel cage machine revolves faster, this is because the squirrel cage machine speed is slightly less than twice the 60Hz synchronous speed of 11800r/min it receives 120Hz power from the rotor of the frequency converter.

The frequency of 30Hz was generated by the wound rotor machine when the rotor was turning at 900r/min in the same direction as the rotating stator magnetic field and the frequency of 90Hz was generated as it was revolving at 900r/min in the opposite to the direction of the rotating field.

When a six-pole wound rotor induction machine was connected with a nominal speed of 1200r/min and driven by a 3600r/min squirrel cage induction machine, the highest frequency that was obtained in the combination was a 60Hz input to the stator of the wound rotor machine creates a magnetic field rotating at 1200r/min, and the squirrel cage machine turns the rotor at 3600r/min in the opposite direction to the rotating stator magnetic field thus, generate a frequency of 240Hz. While the

lowest when the squirrel cage machine turns the rotor at 3600r/min in the same direction as the rotating stator magnetic field, the field cut the rotor winding at 2400r/min and generated frequency of 120Hz.

(There was some slip due to the squirrel cage machines that makes both frequencies became slightly lower.

6.0 CONCLUSION

When the output frequency is doubled, the mechanical power and the electrical power to the stator are equal, and then the rotary frequency converter delivers twice as much as electric power to its load as its stator receives. The difference comes from the source of mechanical power driving factor. This type of rotary frequency converters is employed in industry to generate the higher frequencies necessary to drive small, high-speed squirrel cage machines.

It was observed that the squirrel cage machine revolves faster, this is because the squirrel cage machine speed is slightly less than twice the 60Hz synchronous speed of 1800r/min it receives 120Hz power from the rotor of the frequency converter. As the speed was vary, the rotor was turning at 900r/min in the same direction as the rotating stator magnetic field, only 30Hz frequency would be generated by the wound rotor machine and only frequency of 90Hz would be generated If it were revolving at 900r/min in the opposite to the direction of the rotating field.

When a six-pole industrial rotary frequency converter machine was connected with a nominal speed of 1200r/min and driven by a 3600r/min induction machine, the highest frequency that was obtained in the combination was a 60Hz input to the stator of the industrial rotary frequency converter machine creates a magnetic field rotating at 1200r/min, and the machine turns the rotor at 3600r/min in the opposite direction to the rotating stator magnetic field thus, generate a frequency of 240Hz. While the lowest when the machine turns the rotor at 3600r/min in the same direction as the rotating stator magnetic field, the field cut the rotor winding at 2400r/min and generated frequency of 120Hz. (There was some slip due to the machines that makes both frequencies became slightly lower.

Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter machine speed was increased to drive the industrial machine faster. This was achieved by connecting the stator of the Industrial Rotary Frequency Converter machine to 60Hz power supply and the rotor been driven at 1800r/min by the synchronous machine. The direction of rotation was opposite to that of the resolving magnetic field created by the stator windings and turning the frequency of the rotor output voltage to 120Hz. This is because; the electrical power delivered by a rotary frequency converter that comes from two sources: The electrical power supply to which the stator windings are connected and the mechanical power delivered to rotating rotor shaft. The machine revolves faster in speed and this method can be used to drives an industrial machine where faster and higher speed is requires. This is recommended for machine designers, Engineers and industries when machines require faster and higher speed.

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